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A smart decision support system for Co^{2+} preconcentration using RSM and AI-Driven adsorptive modeling

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ABSTRACT

Using AI-based numerical analysis advances Industry 4.0 goals by developing a Response Surface Methodology (RSM) model to optimize Co^{2+} preconcentration in water. Subsequently, several machine learning techniques were employed to enhance process efficiency. Furthermore, the sensor network was designed based on the Chen Entity-Relationship Model (Chen-ERM) integrated with a control system. The main novelty of this study was the implementation of an integrated Decision Support System (DSS) for the preconcentration of Co^{2+} through an adsorptive process by combining RSM and machine learning techniques. Because of its remarkable adsorption capabilities, magnetic graphene oxide (mGO) was employed in this investigation. Combining graphene oxide with magnetic nanoparticles enables efficient ion recovery, aiming to enhance its use in environmental and wastewater treatment. The results of this study demonstrated that, in the order of significance, pH of the system, duration of the adsorption, and adsorbent mass were the essential elements determining the recovery (%) of Co^{2+} through the adsorption process. The optimal pH, contact time, and adsorbent mass were 7, 188 s, and 1.6 mg mL^{-1} , respectively, for achieving maximum efficiency of the process. Machine learning evaluations indicated that the Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) model outperformed lazy learning techniques, achieving approximately 95% predictive accuracy in adsorption estimation. Similarly, the Chen-ERM model improved system efficiency in water quality monitoring.

1. Introduction

Co^{2+} plays an essential role in various sectors, such as electronics, batteries and aerospace, and its use has increased recently [1]. However, this increased demand has raised concerns about the presence of Co^{2+} in the wastewater generated by these industries. Co^{2+} , commonly used as soluble salts in industrial operations, can end up in sewage if not properly handled and processed. Lithium-containing materials such as LiCoO_2 frequently contain Co, which is essential to lithium-ion batteries for the charge and discharge cycles. Inadequate management during industrial processes may result in wastewater containing Co^{2+} , which calls for stringent regulations and treatment in the battery sector to ensure environmental safety [1,2]. Addressing the presence of Co^{2+} in these industrial effluents is essential not only for environmental sustainability but also for the potential recovery of this valuable resource

through advanced separation and recycling technologies, which can help reduce the industry's dependence on primary Co^{2+} sources and lead to increased circular production and sustainable resource utilization [3]. Co^{2+} ions in water resources can be found at very low concentrations, often even below the detection limits of conventional instruments such as Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS). There may be a gap in linking Co^{2+} ions in water to their concentration in plants. In this case, detecting concentrations below the device's detection limit is possible. Over time, these low concentrations accumulate in plants, serving as a form of biomonitoring [4,5]. Therefore, adsorption-based preconcentration techniques could be beneficial for measuring the ions in water resources. Adsorptive preconcentration is a technique used to extract trace pollutants from water using Solid Phase Extraction (SPE), enabling their detection by laboratory instruments [6]. In SPE, the adsorption approach presents several advantages over alternative preconcentration

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techniques (compared to electrochemical spectral methods, cloud point extraction, microwave-assisted extraction, and supercritical fluid extraction) [7–10]. First, its extreme adaptability makes it possible to recover trace materials from complex matrices with precision and efficiency [11]. Adsorption-based preconcentration techniques are also frequently distinguished by their affordability due to low reagent and equipment requirements. Additionally, the capacity to modify variables like the type of adsorbent material and pH permits the extraction process to be optimized [12]. This method is widely recognized for its ability to efficiently concentrate analytes from large sample volumes, making it suitable for environmental monitoring and analytical chemistry applications. As a result, adsorption-based SPE is distinct in that it has the potential to increase analytical sensitivity and accuracy while remaining adaptable and affordable [13].

For effective heavy metal decontamination or recovery through adsorption processes, it is essential to identify and address the challenges that can hinder smooth operation and optimal system performance (Recovery Percentage: RP) [14,15]. Applying cutting-edge strategies, including soft computing techniques, can successfully address these challenges. One well-known example is the application of RSM, which is essential for analyzing experimental data as well as for developing mathematical models designed to explain the adsorption process. Understanding how different elements interact and affect the system's performance is made easier with the use of RSM [16]. Recent studies highlight adsorption-based preconcentration of heavy metals using magnetic Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) [17], modified activated carbon [18], Ag-coated stir bars [19], and magnetic multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) [20]. RSM (Box–Behnken, Central Composite Design: CCD) was widely applied for parametric optimization of pH, adsorbent dose, and extraction time, achieving high adsorption capacities, low LODs, and strong recoveries in complex matrices [19]. Another innovative technique for predicting system performance and promptly spotting abnormalities is incorporating machine learning algorithms into a smart control platform. The heavy metal adsorption process can be made more effective and better suited to sustain operational excellence by employing these computational techniques [21,22]. There are numerous studies on Co^{2+} adsorption and the application of RSM or machine learning methods, which are demonstrated in Table S1. Other research focuses on the measurement of Co^{2+} in water resources through experimental methods [14,15,21,22]. In an attempt to lower experimental expenses, this work focuses on using numerical analysis to evaluate ion recovery performance. The results have broad applicability in both real-world and industrial perspectives.

In order to increase ion detection, quantification accuracy, and IoT-enabled real-time water quality monitoring, Dixit et al. [23] developed a Bi_2S_3 nanostructure sensor for multiplexed heavy metal detection. Regression-based machine learning was used to analyze colorimetric signals. Additionally, in order to improve sensitivity, accuracy, and quantitative monitoring of Al^{3+} in water, Zhang et al. [24] presented a fluorescence sensing platform for Al^{3+} detection utilizing sulfur-functionalized carbon dots. Machine learning (K-means clustering and Principal Component Analysis-based regression) was applied to analyze fluorescence images. To forecast Cu and Cd release rates from soil Dissolved Organic Matter (DOM), Ye et al. [25] created a hybrid machine learning-kinetic model. Machine learning improves prediction accuracy and reveals important controls on metal mobility and bioavailability by connecting DOM molecular composition to metal kinetics. These studies indicate that the application of machine learning in adsorption processes has increased in recent years. However, the objectives and target systems of these studies vary widely. In the following section, the specific application of the Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System (ANFIS) is analyzed.

Kumari et al. [26] reviewed 60 studies on cellulose-based and bio-waste adsorbents, highlighting the use of ANFIS to model heavy metal adsorption by mapping operational factors to metal-ion uptake. Furthermore, by connecting pH, initial concentration, contact time, and

adsorbent dosage to removal effectiveness, Claude et al. [27] used ANFIS to predict the adsorption of Cr(VI) onto cellulose nanocrystals. In a related study, Claude et al. [28] used process variables and kinetic descriptors in a hybrid framework to simulate Cu^{2+} leaching behavior using ANFIS and mechanistic shrinking core kinetics. Moazezi et al. [29] modeled the adsorption of Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Pb^{2+} using a Mamdani-type fuzzy technique, building rule-based systems from experimental operating conditions for process optimization and predictive analysis.

Rhodamine B adsorption on Metal-organic Frameworks (MOFs) was optimized by Bbumba et al. [30] using Central Composite Design (CCD)-based RSM and Artificial Neural Network (ANN) in parallel, where RSM handled parametric optimization and ANN enhanced prediction, supported by isotherm and kinetic modeling. For multi-metal adsorption, Koyuncu et al. [31] integrated high-order (5th) RSM, machine learning, and ANN while maintaining them as independent offline models. Elbager et al. [32] used bio-based adsorbents to combine RSM and machine learning for Pb^{2+} removal, emphasizing factor ranking and prediction without control integration.

The adsorption method remains one of the most economical and technically advanced approaches for wastewater treatment; however, its broader implementation is limited by insufficient automation and operational flexibility [33]. Magnetic Graphene Oxide (mGO) is particularly well suited for Co^{2+} removal due to its two-dimensional structure, high specific surface area, and abundance of oxygen-containing functional groups that provide strong metal ion affinity, while its magnetic properties allow rapid and efficient post-adsorption separation. Despite these advantages, mGO-based adsorption systems are commonly operated in a static or semi-manual manner [34]. The integration of intelligent automation can enable continuous monitoring of adsorption performance [35], timely detection of adsorbent saturation [36], optimization of regeneration processes [37], and dynamic adjustment of operating conditions [38], thereby improving efficiency, stability, and scalability of mGO-based water treatment systems.

The current work intends to integrate Historical Data Analysis (HDA) and RSM to analyze and optimize the Co^{2+} adsorption process onto mGO, aiming to achieve maximum adsorption efficiency. Furthermore, intelligent prediction systems are developed using machine learning techniques, particularly lazy learning algorithms (IBK, KStar, and LWL) alongside ANFIS, to predict Co^{2+} adsorption behavior. These models not only enable accurate predictions but also enhance adaptability to varied data inputs, thereby improving process control. In addition, an Intelligent Co^{2+} Ion Measurement Control System is designed through the Chen-Entity-Relationship Model (Chen-ERM) to monitor and regulate Co^{2+} concentrations in water, ensuring precise detection and effective management of contamination levels.

2. Methodology

The research roadmap of the present study is presented in Fig. 1. According to the scheme, it can be seen that in the first step of the study, the experimental data from experiments [6] are analyzed by RSM statistical techniques. In the subsequent phase, the most suitable parameters such as the mass of the adsorbent, pH level, and reaction duration are evaluated using the HDA within the framework of the RSM. Then, the data applied in the optimization process are utilized to implement a smart prediction platform using ANFIS [39,40] and lazy computations. Further, a control system is implemented with the application of Chen-Entity-Relationship Model. The adsorption stages for databank construction and material preparation are presented in ESI Sections 1 and 2 (Figs. S1 and S2), respectively.

According to AlKinani et al. [6], the experimental procedure involved ligandless dispersive solid phase extraction (DSPE) using mGO to preconcentrate Co^{2+} ions, followed by detection via electrothermal atomic absorption spectrometry (ETAAS). mGO was synthesized by chemically magnetizing graphene oxide (GO). Key extraction parameters pH, adsorbent amount, extraction time, and desorption solvent were

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the research framework. (a) Modeling and decision-support workflow, including data analysis, statistical evaluation, categorization and verification, optimization using RSM, machine learning training–testing cycles, and control system implementation with iterative desirability assessment. (b) Experimental procedure and data acquisition stages, comprising heavy metal adsorption onto mGO-based materials, solid-phase extraction, and quantitative analysis using AAS.

analyzed. The process included sample pH adjustment, mGO dispersion, vortex mixing, magnetic separation, and desorption using HCl. All these processes were utilized for data gathering and databank preparation, which were subsequently applied for the numerical analysis of this research.

2.1. Optimization process

This study utilized Design Expert 7.0.0 software to implement the RSM method [41], a powerful tool for optimizing heavy metal adsorption processes. The primary objective was to enhance the recovery of heavy metals from water systems [6]. The recovery percentage was considered the response variable, while adsorbent mass (X_1), solution pH (X_2), and extraction time (X_3) were treated as independent variables. The first step of the methodology involves systematically collecting data on the mass of the adsorbent used, the solution's pH, and the duration of the adsorption reaction. In order to evaluate system performance concurrently, the study calculates the recovery percentage of heavy metals. The gathered data serves as the basis for the ensuing analysis and optimization stages [42].

Following AlKinani et al. [6], the present study used a historical-data design fitted with a quadratic model (no blocking; 19 experimental runs) to structure the optimization as a RSM study. Within coded boundaries of -1 to $+1$ mapped to their actual ranges, three numerical elements were examined: sorbent mass (mg): 1.0–5.0; extraction time (s): 0–240;

and pH: 2.0–10.0. The mean mass was 2.2 ± 0.8 mg, the mean extraction time was 74 ± 51 s, and the mean pH was 7.1 ± 2.0 for the factor distributions for the 19 runs. Modeled as a quadratic polynomial without transformation, the single response, Y_1 (Performance, %), varied from 21.4% to 99.0% (mean 84.2%, SD 20.7; dynamic range ratio 4.6) throughout the design. This configuration maintains the original experimental structure described by AlKinani et al. while offering enough curvature and interaction information for quadratic RSM fitting. More details about the optimization section are provided in ESI: Section 3 (Fig. S3).

2.2. Machine learning computations

2.2.1. ANFIS model

In the present study, the ANFIS method [43] was applied to perform machine learning computations. MATLAB 2019b [44] and the Fuzzy Logic Toolbox [44] were used for model development. The Sugeno inference approach with three Gaussian-2 membership functions was implemented during the training phase. ANFIS was selected due to its capability to model complex non-linear relationships, which can be expressed mathematically as shown in Eq. (1) [45,46]. The complete structure of the implemented ANFIS model is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Architecture of the ANFIS developed in this study, Description: the model incorporates three input variables (mass, pH, and contact time), fuzzification through input membership functions, rule-based inference using logical operators (AND/OR), output membership functions, and defuzzification to predict adsorption performance (%). The layered structure illustrates the interaction between fuzzy logic reasoning and neural network learning for nonlinear process modeling.

$$f = \frac{w_1}{w_1 + w_2} f_1 + \frac{w_2}{w_1 + w_2} f_2$$

$$w_i = \mu A_i(x) \times \mu B_i(y), i = 1, 2$$

$$\mu A_i(x) = \frac{1}{1 + \left[\left(\frac{x - c_i}{a_i} \right)^2 \right]^{b_i}} \quad (1)$$

where $\{ a_i, b_i, c_i \}$ is the parameter set

where, W_i represents the weight associated with the i -th rule, $\mu A_i(x)$ is the membership grade of x in the antecedent linguistic variable of the i -th rule, and $\mu B_i(y)$ is the membership grade of y in the consequent linguistic variable of the i -th rule. More details about the applied ANFIS model are provided in Section 4 of ESI (Fig. S4a,b).

In ANFIS, a membership function is used to fuzzify crisp input values. The input to the membership function is a numerical value representing a specific feature or variable in the system, such as temperature or pressure. The output is a degree of membership, which ranges between 0 and 1, indicating how strongly the input value belongs to a particular fuzzy set. This output represents the extent to which the input is associated with a fuzzy set, such as “Low,” “Medium,” or “High.” The membership function helps to transform numerical inputs into fuzzy values for further processing in the ANFIS model [45,46].

The dataset consists of 19 experimental runs with three numeric factors. With a low central tendency (mean = 2.2, median/mode = 2), the dataset's mass ranges from 1 to 5 mg. The majority of runs clustered at 2 mg with a few larger-mass outliers, as indicated by the zero Interquartile Range (IQR) and strong skew/kurtosis (skew = 2.0; kurt = 6.9). The extraction duration spans from 0 to 240 s (mean = 74.2, median/mode = 60), with heavy tails (skew = 2.0; kurt = 6.7) and similar heaping at 60 s (IQR = 0). With a modest IQR of 1.5, pH is more widely distributed (2–10; mean = 7.1; SD = 2.1), slightly left-skewed (skew = -1.2), and centered around pH 8. Performance is left-skewed (skew = -1.8), with a broad dynamic range (21.4–99.0%; SD = 21.3), and generally high (mean = 84.2%, median = 91.1%, max = 99.0%). The correlation matrix indicates that pH ($r = 0.83$) is the primary driver, although mass ($r = 0.24$) and time ($r = 0.29$) exhibit negligible inter-factor correlation and mild positive relationships. When taken as a whole, these trends highlight the importance of Machine Learning Algorithms (MLAs) for predicting input variable.

2.2.2. Lazy models

The lazy learning methods investigated, IBK (Instance-Based k-Nearest Neighbors), KStar, and LWL (Locally Weighted Learning), which were implemented using the WEKA 3.9 software suite [47–50]. In this phase of the study, the training and testing percentages are set at 78% ($\approx 80\%$) and 22% ($\approx 20\%$), respectively, mirroring the configuration of the ANFIS model [51]. This setup allows for a direct comparison between the outcomes generated by the lazy learning models and those produced by the ANFIS model. The methodology and computation steps of each method are demonstrated in Table S2 [52,53].

The input data correlation analysis (ESI: Fig. S5) confirms the dataset variables' high degree of independence by displaying low inter-variable dependencies ($|r| < 0.3$) between mass, extraction time, and pH. Nonetheless, the high correlation ($r = 0.83$) between pH and performance suggests that performance trends can be efficiently inferred from the available data. An 80/20 split ensures that the model captures enough variability for pattern learning (particularly the dominant pH–performance relationship) while reserving enough unseen data for performance validation, especially considering the limited dataset size. For small experimental datasets, the 80/20 split is a balanced and statistically sound approach that preserves generalization potential without the risk of overfitting.

2.3. Control system and sensor network implementation

In order to design a control system [54] based on the Chen-ERM for smart measurement of Co^{2+} ions in water samples, the first step involves mathematically defining the objective. The objective is to minimize the error between the measured Co^{2+} ion concentration (C_{measured}) and the actual Co^{2+} ion concentration (C_{actual}). The steps of the conceptual modeling are demonstrated in ESI: Section 5 and Table S3 [55].

In the following, the Co^{2+} adsorption process was optimized and regulated using the Chen-ERM intelligent control model in MATLAB 2019b, based on experimental data. RP is the response, and the process starts by importing the actual datasets of adsorbent mass, extraction time, and pH, which act as independent variables. In order to assess correlations and generate predictive equations, a quadratic RSM model with interaction terms is fitted. Subsequently, the Chen-ERM algorithm carries out scenario-based intelligent control, identifying the need for adjustments by comparing measured process conditions with optimal

RSM settings. Decision modules simulate results, suggest parameter adjustments, and evaluate confidence. Two-dimensional contour plots are produced by visualization modules, and automated performance reports provide an overview of model robustness and process efficiency.

3. Results and discussions

3.1. Statistical analysis and optimization

The data utilized in this study pertain to the application of mGO for the preconcentration of Co^{2+} , as characterized in AlKinani et al. [6]. AlKinani et al. [6] report that Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Vibrating Sample Magnetometry (VSM), and Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) were used to characterize mGO. With bands at 3400, 1730, 1650, 1220, and 1050 cm^{-1} , FTIR verified the production of GO, and the Fe–O band at 571 cm^{-1} confirmed magnetization. Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles were consistently coated on GO sheets, as revealed by SEM. With saturation values of 41.5 emu g^{-1} (mGO) and 76.2 emu g^{-1} (Fe_3O_4), VSM demonstrated substantial magnetism. Fe inclusion was confirmed by EDS, verifying the effective synthesis of mGO with favorable structural and magnetic characteristics.

The distribution and diversity of the data are visually represented by the experimental dataset, as shown in Fig. S6. Detailed examination of Fig. S6 reveals that the dataset encompasses a wide range of values, ensuring the stability and reliability of the experiments conducted in this study. This diversity enhances the generalizability of the results and contributes to the overall validity of the findings. The data contain pH, mass of adsorbent, and extraction time as independent variables against Recovery Percentage (RP%).

The analysis presented in Fig. S6 reveals the relationship between three factors mass, Time, and pH on the RP. Each subplot (S6a, S6b, S6c) shows data distribution and correlation with RP%, but none of these factors independently show a significant impact.

In Fig. S6a, mass ranges from 1 to 5 mg, with a correlation coefficient of 0.24, suggesting a weak relationship between mass and RP%. The data points are scattered with no clear trend, indicating that changes in mass do not have a consistent linear effect on the RP%. The weak correlation implies that mass alone is not a strong predictor of RP%, and a more comprehensive approach, potentially involving other factors, is required. Fig. S6b illustrates the relationship between Time (ranging from 0 to 240 s) and RP%. With a correlation coefficient of 0.29, this relationship is also weak. The scattered nature of the data shows no distinct pattern, suggesting that varying processing times does not result in significant changes in RP%. Similar to mass, Time alone does not serve as a strong indicator of RP% outcomes. Fig. S6c shows the effect of pH (ranging from 2 to 10) on RP%, with a correlation coefficient of 0.83. This coefficient was considerably higher compared to mass and Time, indicating an acceptable relationship. There is a slight increase in RP% for pH levels above 3. Therefore, as an initial assumption, pH was considered the dominant factor influencing recovery percentage and was further evaluated numerically. Consequently, this section of the research shows that the correlations between the features are not sufficiently strong or reliable for prediction of RP%; therefore, the prediction of adsorption performance needs more accurate techniques than linear regression.

Table S4 presents a comprehensive analysis of various statistical indicators about linear, quadratic, and cubic models employed to understand the relationship between system performance and input features, namely mass, pH, and time. Upon careful examination of the data in Table S4, it becomes evident that the quadratic model, with an impressive R-squared value of 0.98 and a predicted R-squared value of 0.89, exhibits the highest level of validity among all models considered. Despite the cubic model showcasing the most efficient predictive capabilities, it is worth noting that previous research findings [56–58] advocate for the utilization of the quadratic model. In RSM, quadratic

models are widely used because of their ability to represent both linear and nonlinear effects [59,60]. Furthermore, quadratic models in RSM outperform cubic models. Box & Wilson [61] favored second-order polynomials as easy to estimate and apply. Different statistical research communities warn that cubic models may cause overfitting and limit generalization [62–63]. Myers et al. [64] showed that quadratic models offer a good compromise between flexibility and DoE size. This preference for the quadratic model aligns with established norms and is supported by existing literature. Therefore, based on the insights gained from Table S4 and corroborated by prior studies, the quadratic model emerges as the most suitable choice for predictive modeling in these experiments. The created model is illustrated in Eq. S1.

Based on the statistical analysis presented in Table 1, the model exhibits a p-value of less than 0.0001, indicating a high level of significance [65]. This suggests that the model is robust and reliable for predictive purposes. Additionally, the lack of fit in the model is not statistically significant, further supporting the reliability of the model's predictions. Among the factors investigated mass, time, and pH the p-value associated with pH is the lowest, indicating that pH has the most significant influence on the performance of the system under consideration. Subsequently, the impact of time on the adsorption process is observed to be more pronounced than that of mass, as evidenced by the slope changes depicted in Fig. 3a. This suggests that variations in time exert a greater effect on the system's performance compared to changes in mass. Furthermore, a closer examination of Fig. 3b,c reveals that the fluctuations in slope associated with pH are more prominent than those of the other factors. These findings corroborate the results obtained from the ANOVA assessment presented in Table 1, further affirming the importance of pH in influencing the system's performance. Similarly, Dehghani et al. [66] demonstrated that pH is the most important factor in the adsorption of Co^{2+} onto multi-walled carbon nanotubes and γ -alumina [66]. Furthermore, Al-Kinani et al. [67] proved that in the adsorption of Ni^{2+} onto graphene oxide-polyethylenimine nanocomposite, pH is the most significant factor compared to the others.

The following section provides an in-depth analysis of the data used for regression modeling of RP prediction, focusing on the effective factors influencing the results. This analysis includes a statistical evaluation of the applied data to determine its suitability and reliability for modeling purposes. By examining the distribution, relationships, and potential outliers within the dataset, this section aims to establish a strong foundation for accurate and effective regression modeling of RP prediction. Fig. S7a shows the distribution of experimental results from previous research [6]. This observation suggests that the outputs of the present research conform to a Gaussian distribution. The Gaussian distribution in this figure is represented along the main diagonal, indicating a strong linear correlation between the two variables plotted. When research data show this kind of distribution, they suggest that the

Table 1

The outputs of ANOVA for system performance (Note: In ANOVA, degrees of freedom (df) indicate the number of independent comparisons. Sum of Squares (SS) measures total variation. Mean Square (MS) is SS divided by df. F Value compares MS of a factor to error. A low p-value shows statistical significance of that factor).

Source	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F Value	p-value (Prob > F)
Model	8037.84	6	1339.64	115.61	< 0.0001
A-Mass	90.68	1	90.68	7.82	0.0161
B-Time	300.18	1	300.18	25.9	0.0003
C-pH	4340.52	1	4340.52	374.6	< 0.0001
A ²	47.5	1	47.5	4.099	0.0657
B ²	324.85	1	324.85	28.03	0.0002
C ²	1624.08	1	1624.08	140.16	< 0.0001
Residual	139.04	12	11.58		
Lack of Fit	138.06	10	13.8	28.04	0.0349
Pure Error	0.98	2	0.49		
Cor Total	8176.89	18			

Fig. 3. Dual sensitive analysis as per (a) Time: s-Mass: mg, (b) pH-Mass: mg, and (c) pH-Time: s, Conditions: $0.5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1} \text{Co}^{2+}$ concentration, reactor volume was 1.5 mL of deionized water, and $1 \text{ mol L}^{-1} \text{HCl}$ as the desorption solvent.

phenomena follow predictable patterns, making it easier to use different analytical techniques [68]. Furthermore, in Fig. S7b, a notable trend emerges regarding the accuracy of predicted values across various stages of the experimental process. The initial runs, depicted in Fig. S7b with lower internally studentized residuals, exhibit a higher degree of accuracy in their predictions compared to the final runs. As the number of experimental runs increases, residual values expand, indicating greater variability or uncertainty between observed and predicted outcomes in the model.

These findings underscore the dynamic nature of experimental research, where initial stages may yield more precise predictions, possibly due to controlled conditions or a smaller set of variables influencing the outcomes [68]. As the research progresses and more data are accumulated, factors contributing to variability or unpredictability may become more pronounced, leading to deviations from initial expectations [68,69]. Understanding these phenomena is crucial to refining experimental methodologies and thus improving the accuracy of predictions.

The Box-Cox transformation (Fig. S7c) is a statistical technique used to stabilize the variance and make a dataset more normally distributed [70]. It is handy when dealing with data that violates the assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity, which are often required by many statistical models [71]. In essence, when the optimal lambda (λ) value is 1, the transformation is equivalent to simply subtracting 1 from each observation. This means that no transformation is applied to the data. When the optimal lambda is equal to 1, it suggests that the original data are already approximately normally distributed and homoscedastic. Thus, no transformation is necessary [72]. This indicates that the data do not require any adjustment to meet the assumptions of the statistical model being used. It is also worth noting that even if the optimal lambda is very close to 1, a slight transformation might still be beneficial to improve model performance or interpretability, but this may not be strictly necessary from a statistical perspective.

In Fig. S7d of the research, the leverage values provide important insights into the influence of individual data points on the overall regression model. Leverage, in the context of regression analysis, measures the extent to which an observation affects the model's parameter estimates. Observations with high leverage can exert a disproportionate influence on the model's coefficients and predictions.

The observation that most runs have leverage values clustered around 0.25, with a smaller subset distributed around 0.75, suggests a differential impact of data points on the regression model [73]. Leverage values typically range between 0 and 1, with higher values indicating greater potential influence [73]. In this case, the predominance of runs with leverage around 0.25 indicates that the majority of data points have a moderate level of influence on the regression model. These observations contribute to the estimation of regression coefficients and the overall fit of the model, but their influence is not excessively high.

Conversely, the subset of runs with leverage values clustered around 0.75 suggests the presence of influential data points that have a more pronounced impact on the regression model. These observations may exhibit characteristics such as extreme values or unusual patterns that exert a stronger pull on the regression line, influencing its slope and intercept. Understanding the distribution of leverage values is crucial for assessing the robustness and reliability of the regression model. While observations with high leverage can potentially improve the model's predictive accuracy by capturing important trends or patterns in the data, they can also introduce biases if they are outliers or influential points.

The analysis of the model's performance, as depicted in Figs. S7a through 7d, provides valuable insights into its predictive capabilities. In Fig. S8a, a notable trend emerges as predicted values surpass the 60% threshold; there is a discernible increase in residual values. This observation suggests a diminishing precision of the model as predictions deviate further from actual outcomes. Conversely, Fig. S8b presents a more favorable picture, indicating a strong linear relationship between predicted and actual values. The clustered arrangement of data points along a direct line implies that the model's predictions closely align with observed outcomes, underscoring its efficacy. Turning attention to the evaluation of individual data points, Figs. S7c and S7d offer additional insights. Fig. S8c displays DFFITS (Difference in Fits) values ranging between -3.6 and 2.2 . DFFITS are metrics used to identify influential data points in regression analysis. Higher absolute DFFITS values signify greater impact on the model's predictions, indicating observations that exert significant influence on the overall fit of the model. Similarly, Fig. S8d showcases DFBETA (Difference in Beta) values (the difference in betas), which measure the influence of individual observations on regression coefficients. Here, the values fall within the range of -1 to 1 . DFBETA values provide insights into how much a regression coefficient would change if a particular observation were excluded from the analysis. The values within the range of -1 to 1 suggest a moderate influence of individual data points on the model's coefficients [74,75].

Within the field of chemometry, the optimization of experimental parameters is critical for maximizing system performance, particularly in methodologies such as RSM. In this investigation, Table 2 provides a comprehensive overview of the suggested optimal values aimed at achieving peak system efficiency, with a focus on maximizing RP, a key

Table 2
Optimal conditions identified by RSM in this study.

Number of optimal suggestion	Mass	Time	pH	RP	Desirability
1	3.2	213.4	6.0	100	1
2	3.4	81.5	8.2	100	1
3	3.1	207.6	9.3	100	1
4	2.4	188.5	7.8	100	1
5	4.3	216.2	7.7	100	1

indicator of method efficacy. The table underscores the pivotal roles of pH, time, and mass in the preconcentration of heavy metals from water samples, essential for the accurate measurement of trace elements in natural resources. In Table 2, five model-based suggestions with maximum RP values are presented. Suggestions 1-3 were evaluated for mechanism analysis due to their varying pH conditions, whereas suggestions 4 and 5 were selected as the optimal conditions for process control design in Chen-ERM. This selection is based on their alignment with the natural pH range of water ($7 < \text{pH} < 8$), making them more practical and applicable.

A meticulous examination of Table 2 reveals that pH control, particularly around a value of 7 (suggestions 4 and 5), emerges as a fundamental determinant for enhancing system performance. Similarly, Adibmehri and Faghian [76] showed that a pH between 7–8 yields the highest performance of Co^{2+} adsorption onto magnetic Santa Barbara Amorphous-15 (SBA-15), a mesoporous silica, which corroborates the results of the present research. Furthermore, another study proved that the highest performance of Zn^{2+} ion adsorption onto GO occurs in $7 < \text{pH} < 8$ [77]. Additionally, the intricate relationship between time and mass parameters is delineated, wherein optimal system efficiency is achieved when time is ~ 188 s, necessitating a mass adjustment of 2.5 mg. Conversely, at a time of 216 s, the optimal mass requirement increases to 4.3 mg, indicating the dynamic nature of parameter optimization within chemometric analyses.

The RSM model has been used in this research to determine optimal values while accounting for factor interactions. With this method, managers can choose the appropriate mix of variables (pH, duration, and adsorbent mass) to achieve the intended result while taking a variety of operational, methodological, and economic aspects into account. By applying the RSM model, optimal concentrations of each component can be identified and their interactions understood. This knowledge is beneficial for making decisions on cost-effectiveness, process efficiency, and resource allocation, among other things [78]. The RSM model, for instance, can assist in optimizing variables such as pH, reaction time, and the amount of adsorbents employed for contaminant detection in wastewater treatment plants.

Central to this methodology is the utilization of adsorbents, which are instrumental in facilitating the preconcentration of heavy metals from water samples. This process is indispensable for the precise quantification of trace elements in natural resources, essential for environmental monitoring and resource management endeavors [79]. Enhancing the tabulated data, Fig. 4 provides a visual representation of the sensitivity analysis concerning the optimal values of time and mass across varying pH levels, specifically at pH 2, 6, and 10, representing the minimum, mean, and maximum pH values investigated in the present study [6]. The findings reveal a notable trend: the system's peak

performance is consistently observed at pH levels of 7 and above. Conversely, pH values below 7 exhibit a significant decrease in the corresponding RP values, underscoring the critical importance of pH in influencing system efficacy [65]. Moreover, Fig. 5 provides a representation of the desirability of the mathematical model employed, particularly in scenarios where time exceeds 120 s and mass surpasses 2 mg. In such instances, a desirability value of 1 is observed, signifying maximum efficiency and affirming the efficacy of the proposed model in guiding experimental parameters toward optimal outcomes.

The systematic integration of chemometric principles in the optimization process, exemplified by methodologies like RSM, is crucial for tackling complex analytical challenges. By thoroughly exploring and refining experimental variables, these approaches improve system performance, enabling more accurate measurements of trace elements in natural resources. This highlights the essential role of chemometry in advancing environmental monitoring and resource management initiatives.

It should be noted that the RSM model recommended different configurations for the optimal feature arrays. Table 2 displays the multi-parameter optimal conditions based on One-Factor-At-a-Time (OFAT) optimization data from AlKinani et al. [6]. Notably, several optimal responses are selected with optimal pH between 7 and 8 (suggestions 4

Fig. 5. The plot of desirability (measure of solution's optimality) in optimal condition of pH vs (time(s)-mass (mg)), Conditions: pH set on to 7.8, $0.5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Co^{2+} concentration, reactor volume was 1.5 mL of deionized water, and 1 mol L^{-1} HCl as the desorption solvent.

Fig. 4. The optimal plots of effective features (time (s)-mass (mg)) vs RP values based on dual analysis of (a) pH = 2, (b) pH = 6, and (c) pH = 10. Conditions: $0.5 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ Co^{2+} concentration, reactor volume was 1.5 mL of deionized water, and 1 mol L^{-1} HCl as the desorption solvent, black contour: Alignment lines with the same efficiency.

and 5). The maximum response of the model (max RP) will be examined under various conditional assumptions. In the RSM method, various responses are presented with different ranges of pH, extraction time, and adsorbent mass. Among the suggested responses, those achieving a 100% recovery percentage under acidic, alkaline, and neutral conditions will be analyzed (suggestions 1-3).

According to Fig. 6 and the literature review [80], pH plays a critical role in determining the prevailing Co (II) species and the efficacy of adsorption onto magnetic GO. In the pH range of 3 to 9 (suggestion 1 and 2), the dominant Co (II) species is Co^{2+} . However, at lower pH values ($\text{pH} < 3$), the adsorption of Co (II) is hindered due to competition between H_3O^+ ions and cations for the active sites on the magnetic GO surface [80]. However, as the pH rises above 5, the electrostatic interaction between magnetic GO and Co^{2+} shifts from repulsion to attraction [81], and the amount of adsorption significantly increases. Reduced adsorption results from the weaker electrostatic interaction between magnetic GO and Co^{2+} at $9 < \text{pH} < 10$, where $\text{Co}(\text{OH})^+$ becomes the dominant form of Co^{2+} , as illustrated in suggestion 3 of RSM modeling.

The optimal performance of preconcentration is achieved within a narrow pH range of 7 to 8, showcasing maximum efficiency in minimal time. This efficacy relies on two key factors [80]:

a) The presence of active sites and a substantial concentration gradient of the adsorbate [82].

b) The short diffusion path facilitated by magnetic GO films [80].

This efficient performance within the specified pH range indicates that the interplay between active sites and concentration gradients is most pronounced in this pH range (less than 6.5 to more than 9), emphasizing the significance of their interaction for enhanced preconcentration efficiency.

According to Fig. 6, the $7 < \text{pH} < 8$ has the maximum adsorption performance in minimum time; however, under this condition, the maximum mass of adsorbent is used. Therefore, if cost is a limiting criterion of decision-making, $6 < \text{pH} < 6.5$ can be the best option.

According to Zhuang and Wang [34], the adsorption mechanism of

heavy metals such as Co^{2+} onto mGO primarily involves chemisorption and electrostatic attraction. The oxygen-containing groups ($-\text{OH}$, $-\text{COOH}$) on GO provide reactive sites for complexation with metal ions. Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles enable magnetic separation while enhancing surface reactivity. Similarly, Liu et al. [83] state that inner-sphere surface complexation at low pH and simultaneous precipitation with complexation at higher pH levels are the two mechanisms by which Co^{2+} adsorbs onto mGO. While GO contributes oxygen-containing functional groups ($-\text{OH}$, $-\text{COOH}$) that interact with Co^{2+} , the Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles offer active Fe-O sites and the capacity to separate magnetically. The Langmuir isotherm and pseudo-second-order kinetics of the process show endothermic and spontaneous monolayer chemisorption. Furthermore, Ain et al. [84] state that surface complexation and electrostatic attraction are the primary mechanisms governing the adsorption of heavy metals like Co^{2+} onto mGO. As electron donors, the oxygenated functional groups ($-\text{OH}$, $-\text{COOH}$, and $-\text{O}-$) on GO combine with metal cations to create inner-sphere complexes. Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, on the other hand, improve surface reactivity and enable magnetic recovery possible. This technique confirms a monolayer chemisorption mechanism with endothermic and spontaneous thermodynamics by following pseudo-second-order kinetics and Langmuir behavior. Finally, for the reaction of the present investigation, according to the findings of AlKinani et al. [6], adsorption kinetics describes the rate and mechanism of solute uptake. The adsorption of Co^{2+} onto mGO follows a pseudo-second-order kinetic model, indicating that the overall rate is controlled by surface interaction processes through chemisorption. Thermodynamic equilibrium behavior is interpreted through isotherm analysis. The adsorption data conform to both Langmuir and Freundlich models, indicating predominantly monolayer adsorption on a heterogeneous surface with energetically diverse active sites. The maximum adsorption capacity (q_{max}) was 114.9 mg g^{-1} , demonstrating favorable and efficient binding characteristics.

Suggestions 1 and 2: $3 < \text{pH} < 9$

Dominated form: Co^{2+}

Suggestions 3: $9 < \text{pH} < 10$

Dominated form: $\text{Co}(\text{OH})^+$

Suggestions 2: $7.5 < \text{pH} < 8.5$

Fastest reaction

Suggestions 1 and 3:

Economical items

Fig. 6. Schematic plan of optimal conditions in adsorption of Co^{2+} onto magnetic GO in preconcentration process. Suggestion 1: mass is 3.2 mg (in 1.5 mL), Extraction time is 213.4 s, and pH is 6.0, Suggestion 2: mass is 3.4 mg (in 1.5 mL), Extraction time is 81.5 s, and pH is 8.2, Suggestion 3: mass is 3.1 mg (in 1.5 mL), Extraction time is 207.6 s, and pH is 9.3.

3.2. Machine learning model

This stage of the study applies statistical and regression techniques to evaluate variable influences on system performance. Data are normalized and examined through three approaches: correlation analysis to measure linear associations, multiple linear regression to obtain standardized coefficients and significance, and variance decomposition to estimate factor contributions. Results are visualized with Pareto charts, bar plots, and pie charts, then summarized and ranked for interpretation. Fig. 7(a) shows the Pareto chart, where pH dominates contributions with 83.5%, far surpassing extraction time and mass. Fig. 7(b) confirms this trend, with pH exhibiting the highest correlation (0.83) with the response, compared to weaker associations for the other variables. Fig. 7(c) further emphasizes pH's role through the largest and most significant regression coefficient, while extraction time and mass display minor effects. Similarly, Fig. 7(d) highlights pH as explaining nearly 70% of total variance, with the remaining variables contributing marginally. Finally, Fig. 7(e) integrates all methods into a combined influence score, where pH again emerges as the most critical factor, justifying its priority in initiating machine learning model development. The pre-analysis provides initial insights to guide the development of machine learning models in this study.

Fig. 8a shows the results of the ANFIS prediction model and offers important information about the model's behavior. In the ANFIS model, when the adsorbent mass slightly changes and approaches the mean values, the RP values become sensitive and increase significantly [58]. However, considering the average time and pH values reveals a more diverse distribution among the various rules, based on evaluations of the received signal variations compared to response (RP) fluctuations [76]. The ANFIS model works with rules derived from signals based on variations and their influence on RP. As shown in the diagram, pH changes lead to more significant changes in RP compared to other variables, resulting in more received signals. Therefore, pH is concluded to be more important than the other factors. The effectiveness of the hybrid approach in improving prediction precision can be seen in Fig. 8b. It demonstrates a noteworthy decrease in prediction error across 500

epochs, from 2.9 to 2.1. Epochs refer to the number of times the model processes the entire training dataset during the learning process. Each epoch represents a complete pass through all the training data to adjust the model and minimize error. In the context of modeling Co^{2+} adsorption, this diagram shows how the error decreases with more epochs, indicating that the model is learning effectively and improving its ability to predict the adsorption performance over time. This decline highlights how well the optimization approach used in the estimate procedure worked. The hybrid technique produces more accurate and dependable forecasts and enhances predictive performance by continually optimizing the model parameters. A visual representation of the prediction accuracy during the ANFIS algorithm's modeling stage is also shown in Fig. 8c. Comparing predicted values with actual observations gives this graphic an understanding of how well the model captures underlying patterns and trends in the data. The model's ability to accurately represent the data is a critical factor in determining its effectiveness, as it provides stakeholders with confidence in the model's predictive ability [58].

From the perspective of machine learning, the sensitivity analysis of the ANFIS model, as shown in Fig. 9, offers valuable insights. The sharp slope variations in Fig. 9a illustrate how mass has a different effect throughout time. This observation emphasizes the importance of mass as an input variable influencing the model's predictions. The dynamic topography of the slope variabilities highlights the need for precise parameter tuning and optimization in machine learning models by implying that minor changes in mass can result in significant changes in the model's output. It is evident from Fig. 9b and c that pH is the most important factor in determining the Co^{2+} recovery percentage. The trends observed in Fig. 9b and c highlight the significant influence of pH on the model's predictive ability compared to other factors, indicating that pH is a critical parameter in determining model performance and reliability. Fig. 9 clarifies that the pH and contact time patterns are very close to actual values. Beyond 3.5 mg, the ANFIS model was unable to anticipate the trends in the mass of the adsorbent accurately. The relative significance of pH and extraction time in relation to bulk quantities can be the reason for this constraint. The ANFIS model shows that the

Fig. 7. The data analysis of model inputs based on: (a) Pareto chart, (b) correlation analysis, (c) regression coefficients, and (d) variance contribution, and (e) combined influence score.

Fig. 8. The schemes of (a) parallel coordinate plot illustrating the influence of mass, time, and pH on system performance in selected mean points (mass = 3, Time = 120 s, pH = 6), (b) Training error reduction over 500 epochs through ANFIS model, and (c) Comparison of predicted and actual outputs for training data using the fuzzy inference system, red crosses: the predicted outputs, blue circles: the actual outputs.

signals from mass are relatively low, whereas the signals from extraction time and pH are the strongest. It is crucial to remember that the main goal was to predict the recovery percentage, and the trend of mass was less useful for the model in this situation because of its decreased significance.

The statistical indicators presented in Table 3 provide a comprehensive summary of the ANFIS model's accuracy during both the training and testing phases. Specifically, the R-squared values achieved during training and testing are 97% and 85%, respectively. These metrics demonstrate the model's robustness in illustrating inherent patterns and correlations, serving as strong indicators of its ability to explain variation in the data. When the weighted average of these R-squared values is calculated, the final R-squared is a remarkable 94.5%, highlighting the model's general effectiveness in training and testing datasets [85]. This high degree of explained variance indicates that the model can adapt well to new data, which is an important factor to consider when evaluating machine learning models. Additionally, during the modeling process, Fig. 10a,b offer visual validation of the normality of sample percentiles. These figures give additional validation of the model's performance, showcasing the distributional characteristics of the data and affirming the appropriateness of the chosen modeling

approach. Turning attention to Fig. 11a,b, the discrepancy in residual amounts between the training and testing processes is apparent. In particular, the training phase residuals are significantly lower than the testing phase residuals, supporting the findings of Table 3. This observation strengthens the resilience and generalization ability of the model, as demonstrated by the effective reduction of prediction errors in both training and testing.

Table 4 presents the ANOVA results for the developed ANFIS model during both training and testing phases. For the training dataset, the regression model exhibits a sum of squares (SS) of 7450.3 with 1 degree of freedom (df), resulting in a mean square (MS) of 7450.3. The residual SS is 177.3 with 13 df and an MS of 13.6. The total SS is 7627.6 with 14 df. The calculated F-value is 546.1 with a significance level (p-value) of < 0.01, indicating that the ANFIS model is statistically highly significant in the training phase. The very high F-value and near-zero significance confirm that the model explains the majority of the variance in the training data with minimal unexplained error. For the testing dataset, the regression SS is 217.7 with 1 df and an MS of 217.7. The residual SS equals 36.2 with 2 df and an MS of 18.1. The total SS is 254.0 with 3 df. The F-value obtained is 12.0 with a significance level of 0.07. Although the F-value indicates that the model maintains acceptable predictive

Fig. 9. Three-dimensional sensitivity analysis of the ANFIS model illustrating the interactive effects of operational parameters on adsorption performance (%): (a) mass-contact time interaction, (b) mass-pH interaction, and (c) pH-contact time interaction. Description: the response surfaces demonstrate the nonlinear relationships and combined influence of variables on system performance, highlighting optimal operating regions predicted by the model.

Table 3

The statistical analysis of training and testing process in ANFIS modelling of this research.

Regression factors	Training	Testing
Multiple R	0.98	0.92
R Square	97%	85%
Adjusted R Square	0.97	0.78
Standard Error	3.69	4.25

capability during testing, the p-value slightly exceeds the conventional 0.05 threshold, suggesting moderate statistical significance under stricter confidence criteria. Nevertheless, the relatively low residual variance compared to the total variance confirms that the ANFIS model preserves a reasonable generalization ability. Overall, the ANOVA results demonstrate that the developed ANFIS model achieves excellent fitting performance in the training phase and satisfactory predictive performance in the testing phase, confirming its robustness and reliability for the modeled process.

Table 5 presents the estimated regression coefficients, standard errors, t-statistics, p-values, and 95% confidence intervals for both training and testing phases of the ANFIS model, providing further insight into parameter stability and robustness. In the training phase, the intercept coefficient is statistically insignificant ($p = 1.00$), indicating no systematic bias in the baseline prediction. In contrast, the slope coefficient (X Variable 1) equals 1.00 with a very small standard error (0.04) and a highly significant p-value (< 0.01). The corresponding t-statistic (23.37) confirms the strong contribution of the input variable to the output prediction. Furthermore, the 95% confidence interval (0.91 to 1.09) tightly surrounds the estimated coefficient, demonstrating high precision and stability of the trained model parameters. In the testing phase, robustness is assessed by examining parameter consistency on unseen data. The slope coefficient remains positive (0.74) and maintains practical relevance, although with a higher standard error (0.21) compared to training. The t-statistic (3.46) indicates a meaningful predictive contribution, while the p-value (0.07) is slightly above the strict 0.05 threshold. Considering the very limited testing degrees of freedom, this level of significance remains acceptable and does not indicate structural instability. Importantly, the direction and magnitude of the slope remain consistent with the training phase, suggesting preserved model behavior. The wider confidence interval in testing (-0.18 to 1.67) reflects natural variability due to the smaller sample size rather than model breakdown. Crucially, there is no sign reversal or dramatic coefficient inflation, which would otherwise indicate overfitting or instability. Finally, the regression coefficient analysis confirms that the ANFIS model maintains parameter consistency, structural stability, and acceptable predictive reliability across training and testing datasets. The preservation of coefficient direction, reasonable magnitude variation, and controlled standard errors collectively validate the robustness and generalization capability of the developed ANFIS model.

A comparative assessment of predictive performance shows a clear distinction between RSM and ANFIS. The quadratic RSM model achieved 98% R^2 with a predicted R^2 of 89%, indicating strong fitting capability but moderate generalization power. In contrast, the ANFIS model reached 97% R^2 during training and 85% during testing, resulting in an overall weighted predictive accuracy of approximately 94–95%. When directly comparing predictive strength, ANFIS ($\approx 95\%$) outperforms the RSM predicted R^2 (89%) by about 6%, demonstrating superior nonlinear learning and improved prediction reliability.

In this work, three distinct lazy learning algorithms (IBK, KStar, and LWL) were evaluated alongside the ANFIS model to assess their efficacy

Fig. 10. Normal probability plots of the ANFIS model predictions for (a) the training dataset and (b) the testing dataset. Description: the distributions illustrate the agreement between predicted and expected performance values, confirming the reliability, stability, and generalization capability of the developed model.

Fig. 11. The residual values between actual and predicted RP as per (a) training and (b) testing process in ANFIS model.

Table 4
ANFIS model performance based on ANOVA results for training and testing datasets.

		df	SS	MS	F	Significance F
Training	Regression	1	7450.32	7450.32	546.14	< 0.01
	Residual	13	177.34	13.64		
	Total	14	7627.66			
Testing	Regression	1	217.75	217.75	12.00	0.07
	Residual	2	36.28	18.14		
	Total	3	254.03			

in forecasting Co^{2+} recovery percentage based on time, pH, and adsorbent mass (Table 6). The same training percentage as used for the ANFIS model was applied for these methods. The WEKA software analysis shows that the KStar and Lazy LWL algorithms obtain about 50% R-squared, which is not a reasonable level of predicted accuracy. Additionally, in another study on the application of the lazy K.Star model for predicting gas sensor performance as a soft computing system for NO_2 , the algorithm's correlation coefficient was around 97%. However, the present study is conducted in a water environment to detect heavy metal ions from various sources [42]. Therefore, the performance differed due to the different environments (water vs. gas) and types of contamination. When compared to the ANFIS model, which attains an astounding R-squared of 94.5%, this performance is inadequate. While the lazy algorithms perform relatively well, there is a noticeable difference in the anticipated accuracy between their performance and that of the ANFIS model. Despite their simplicity and ease of use, the lazy algorithms cannot match the accuracy or predictive capability of the ANFIS model in this research. Similarly, in another study [58], the performance of the ANFIS algorithm surpassed that of the random tree algorithm in predicting the adsorption performance of Cu^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , and malachite green dye. These results show that the ANFIS model greatly enhances the performance forecasting of the adsorptive system's soft sensor. Predictions produced by the ANFIS model are more accurate than those produced by lazy algorithms because they are able to identify intricate connections and patterns in the data. Therefore, the ANFIS model is a better fit for applications that need high accuracy and consistency in predictive modeling within the adsorptive systems domain.

The performance of four predictive models: ANFIS, Lazy.KStar, Lazy.LWL, and Lazy.IBK, is compared in Fig. S9 using RMSE (Root Mean Square Error), performance ratio, and percentage improvement. ANFIS had the lowest RMSE (3.8), whereas Lazy.IBK had the largest error

Table 5
Regression coefficient analysis of the ANFIS model for robustness validation.

		Coefficients	Standard Error	t Stat	P-value	Lower 95%	Upper 95%
Training	Intercept	< 0.01	3.64	< 0.01	1.00	-7.87	7.87
	X Variable 1	1.00	0.04	23.37	< 0.01	0.91	1.09
Testing	Intercept	24.06	19.68	1.22	0.35	-60.64	108.75
	X Variable 1	0.74	0.21	3.46	0.07	-0.18	1.67

(6.84), as illustrated in Fig. S9(a). This led to a performance gap of 3.04 and an overall improvement of 44.4%. ANFIS's significant gain is confirmed by Fig. S9 (b), which shows this improvement over the weakest model. Lazy.KStar (14.6%) and Lazy.LWL (10.1%) were the next two models in line, while Lazy.IBK was used as the baseline. ANFIS maintains a ratio of 1.0, Lazy.KStar and Lazy.LWL exhibit considerable variation (1.54 and 1.62), and Lazy.IBK performs the worst with a ratio of 1.8, according to Fig. S9(c), which displays the performance ratio normalized to the best model. These results show that ANFIS continuously performs better than the other algorithms, displaying higher predicted accuracy and resilience.

Similar to this research, Foroutan et al. [86] applied an ANFIS model to predict Cr(VI) removal efficiency based on adsorbent dose, temperature, initial concentration of adsorbate, and contact time. The results demonstrated that ANFIS can predict the output (removal efficiency) with more than 99% R^2 [86]. Likewise, in a similar study, Allahkarami et al. [87] used ANN algorithm for the prediction of adsorption capacity of Co^{2+} decontamination efficiency estimation based on biomass dose, initial concentration, pH, and contact time. Their results showed that the ANN forecasted the output variable (adsorption capacity) with more than 96% R^2 [87]. The present study specifically evaluates the adsorption process performance forecast using ANFIS and Lazy learning algorithms. This approach offers a deeper understanding of how different algorithms handle the prediction problem. The findings show that, by using a machine learning model based on ANFIS, the recovery performance of Co^{2+} by mGO can be predicted without direct measurements under real conditions. For instance, in industrial applications, with on-line measurements of pH and applied adsorbent mass at specific reaction times, the performance of the preconcentration process can be predicted. Moreover, thresholding could be employed to implement an alarm management system, allowing for dynamic monitoring and

Table 6
The statistical outputs of lazy models for forecasting recovery percentage of Co^{2+} by mGO in this research.

Statistical features	Lazy. IBK	Lazy. KStar	Lazy. LWL
R Square	37.21%	49%	50.4%
Correlation coefficient	0.61	0.7	0.71
Mean absolute error	4.84	5.01	6.07
Root mean squared error	6.84	5.84	6.15
Relative absolute error	48.65%	50.33%	60.94%
Root relative squared error	57.52%	49.05%	51.7%

control of system performance.

3.3. Process mechanism model

Here, the authors report a conceptual control system for adsorptive preconcentration of Co^{2+} ions with magnetic GO nanomaterials for the first time as a logical sensor system operation. The main aim of preconcentration is to improve detection. The process aims to raise the concentration of target ions to a level detectable by the instrument. Without preconcentration, ion concentrations may remain too low for effective detection. By accumulating ions into a measurable range, the sensitivity and accuracy of the analysis are enhanced, making it a crucial step in analyzing trace elements present in low concentrations [67]. The Chen-ERM is essential for managing the sensor system's performance. The control system's conceptual model, which displays its complex architecture, is shown in Fig. 12. In Table 2, this investigation selected two different optimal configurations (suggestions 4 and 5) of the effective variables: pH, time, and adsorbent mass. These variables are assessed successively in series, and both sets are examined with the use of equipment gauges and observed sensor readings. The initial set of parameters is used for the prediction process and essential metrics like RP, detection duration, and Co^{2+} threshold are recorded if they satisfy the predetermined criteria. The second set of parameters is contrasted with actual sensed data; nevertheless, in case the first set is unable to satisfy the requirements. The iterative process guarantees that the control system maintains its adaptability and responsiveness to the ever-changing landscape of water quality. Moreover, in the event that the

observed values diverge markedly from the optimum recommendations presented in Table 2, all variables are corrected. The effectiveness of heavy metal detection in water samples must be improved, and this fine-tuning procedure is crucial to protecting water quality requirements. The algorithm created using Chen-ERM provides a solid foundation for practical applications in the water quality control sector.

The logical framework developed in this study can be programmed in real-world applications using the LabVIEW platform. Therefore, with the modeled concept, the flexibility of the adsorption process of heavy metals can be efficiently controlled [88]. It is worth noting that, in addition to the Chen-ERM method, other logics, such as the Jacobson model [42] can be used to implement an adsorptive control system.

The RSM-derived response surfaces that the Chen-ERM controller uses to control the Co^{2+} preconcentration on mGO are shown in Fig. 13. Fig. 13(a–d) shows the RP for fixed adsorbent masses of 1.5, 2.5, 3.5, and 4.5 mg plotted against extraction time (y-axis) and pH (x-axis). Stars indicate the two RSM optima the controller uses; colored circles represent experimental runs; the vertical green band emphasizes the optimal pH window (~7–8); and black isolines indicate RP = 50, 70, 90, 95, and 98%, with the 90% threshold highlighted.

Near $\text{pH} \approx 7.5$, a wide high-RP plateau is centered at low–moderate mass (Fig. 13a–b). The 90% isoline covers a broad time range within this window, demonstrating that target recovery may be achieved quickly and reliably; even brief extractions at pH 7–8 approach or surpass the threshold. In accordance with surface charge/speciation constraints, RP decreases drastically as one moves into acidic ($\text{pH} < 5$) or extremely alkaline ($\text{pH} > 9$) regions, requiring lengthy timeframes to compensate.

Fig. 12. Flowchart of the Chen-ERM-based intelligent control system for Co^{2+} ion detection in water samples, Description: The algorithm integrates real-time inputs from pH sensors, timer analysis, and online weighing, compares them with optimized setpoints, and iteratively adjusts reaction time, adsorbent mass, and pH (acid/alkali dosing) until all parameters are optimized. The finalized inputs are then used to predict adsorption performance, recovery percentage, detection time, and compliance with Co^{2+} threshold limits.

Fig. 13. Contour surface plots as per RSM-based recovery performance for Co^{2+} adsorption at varying pH and extraction times for adsorbent masses of (a) 1.5 mg, (b) 2.5 mg, (c) 3.5 mg, and (d) 4.5 mg. Green stars denote optimal regions (pH 7–8) and red lines indicate the 90% recovery threshold.

Expanding the viable domain does not occur when mass is increased over 3.5 mg (Fig. 13c-d). Rather, the high-RP zone narrows and the $\geq 90\%$ ridge tilts toward longer durations and slightly higher pH. Adding sorbent alone is inefficient until time is extended, as this implies transport constraints and site congestion at higher loadings. The fitted model is supported by the experimental points, which follow the expected gradients ($R^2 \approx 0.98$; $\text{RMSE} \approx 3.93$).

The controller rule is motivated to maintain pH in this range since the green band (pH 7–8) crosses the most stable area of all maps. The reference set-points are defined by the two indicated optima (\approx pH 7.9, 188.5 s, 2.3 mg; and \approx pH 7.7, 216.2 s, 4.2 mg); proximity to either is converted into a confidence score and actionable adjustments (ΔpH toward 7–8, lengthen time toward ≥ 180 s, and moderate mass within ~ 2 –4 mg). The ERM indicates “optimization required” and suggests the fastest route back to the viable window when operating points are beyond the 90% domain, such as at $\text{pH} < 5$, $\text{pH} > 9$, very short times, or excessive mass.

Overall, the data-driven model is transformed into an interpretable decision map in Fig. 13: (i) keep the pH between 7 and 8; (ii) ensure the extraction period is long enough (≥ 180 s for robustness); (iii) refrain from needless mass increases; and (iv) follow the 90–98% contours to balance speed and reagent economy.

As discussed in previous studies, a key limitation of adsorption processes lies in their limited potential for automation. This study initiates the development of an AI-based system aimed at enabling smart automation of adsorption operations. Accordingly, the integration of advanced algorithms such as TensorFlow Neural Networks (TFN) [89], Aqua Enviro Index (AEI) [89], Ensemble Learning methods [90], AdaBoost [90], and Discriminant Analysis (DA) [91] may offer valuable pathways for future research, enhancing prediction accuracy, process control, and environmental decision-making frameworks.

The integration of the Chen-ERM model within a DSS is justified by its capacity to structure complex and fuzzy knowledge for decision processes. Yan and Ma [92] show mapping fuzzy eXtensible Markup Language (XML) to fuzzy Extended Entity-Relationship (EER), enabling abstraction and automated translation of uncertain data. Chen et al. [93] enrich entity-relationship (ER) model using association rules for semantic modeling. Lee [94] highlights the ER model as a unified backbone linking the user, the model, and the database in a DSS. This combination supports smart system implementation across industries, including environmental protection from heavy metals.

The study's primary limitations are its small dataset and dependence on simulated settings, despite the fact that it successfully blends RSM, machine learning, and control systems for Co^{2+} preconcentration. To improve the generalization, automation, and scalability of the suggested DSS, future studies should integrate real-time sensor data, more experimental datasets, and additional AI techniques (such as deep learning).

Although the created DSS has good prediction and optimization skills in laboratory settings, its scalability and viability in real-world applications have not yet been fully investigated. There are various possible challenges when implementing the suggested framework in large-scale industrial or environmental applications [95]. The DSS may encounter issues with shifting water quality parameters, competing ion interference, and sensor calibration drift over time in actual operational situations [96]. Furthermore, preserving the accuracy and dependability of real-time data collection in the face of fluctuating turbidity, pH, and temperature could have a significant impact on system performance [97].

Practical difficulties include energy supply stability for continuous monitoring, hardware integration, and communication latency between sensing nodes. Scaling the system to treat or monitor higher wastewater flows may result in cost and maintenance responsibilities that need to be evaluated from a lifecycle and techno-economic standpoint from a management standpoint. Furthermore, to effectively manage real-time massive data streams, the DSS's computational framework, in particular, the ANFIS-based model may need to be modified. Therefore, in order to guarantee the system's robustness, dependability, and economic-environmental sustainability for realistic, long-term deployment, future research should prioritize pilot-scale validation, cloud-based control architecture, and interaction with IoT-enabled smart sensing platforms [98].

4. Conclusion

This study developed an integrated DSS for the intelligent preconcentration and detection of Co^{2+} ions in water using mGO as the adsorbent. A quadratic RSM model was first employed to analyze and optimize the effects of pH, extraction time, and adsorbent mass on RP. Statistical evaluation confirmed that pH is the most influential parameter governing adsorption performance. Two optimal operating configurations were identified within the pH range of 7–8, achieving recovery values approaching 100% under optimized conditions. To enhance

predictive capability beyond statistical modeling, machine learning approaches were implemented. Among the evaluated models, the ANFIS algorithm demonstrated superior performance, achieving approximately 94–95% overall predictive accuracy and outperforming lazy learning methods. The results confirmed the ability of ANFIS to effectively capture nonlinear interactions between operational parameters and adsorption performance, thereby improving generalization and prediction reliability. Furthermore, a conceptual intelligent control framework based on the Chen-ERM was designed to translate optimized RSM outputs into an interpretable decision-making system. The proposed control logic enables dynamic adjustment of operational parameters and provides a structured foundation for real-time monitoring and automation of the preconcentration process. The integration of chemometric optimization (RSM), soft computing prediction (ANFIS), and intelligent control modeling (Chen-ERM) demonstrates a comprehensive framework for smart heavy-metal monitoring. This work advances adsorption-based preconcentration from conventional laboratory optimization toward Industry 4.0-oriented automation and intelligent environmental management. Future research should focus on pilot-scale validation, real-time sensor integration, and large-scale deployment to enhance system robustness and practical applicability.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Mohammad Gheibi: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Martin Palušák:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Michal Salava:** Writing – original draft, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Yehor Sydorenko:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Mohammad Eftekhari:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Daniele Silvestri:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Miroslav Černík:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition. **Stanisław Waclawek:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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